

Economic and Fishing Activities of Women in Coastal Villages of Nagapattinam District

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Abstract

Women's employment is very often more precarious and less well paid than men's. There has been seen considerable progress worldwide in advancing women's economic, social and cultural rights. Social scientists and development practitioners have long been interested in the conditions that empower women. In this study an attempt has been made about the involvement of fisher women in their economic development. The study area taken for the study is Nagapattinam district of Tamil Nadu. It is a coastal district having a large coast line of 187 kilometers. The parameters taken for development of fisher women economic status are, fishermen death related benefits, awareness about women self help groups, membership of women self help groups and benefits from self help groups. The early studies, particularly of late nineteenth century anthropologists had recorded women's participation in all aspects of social, economic, political and religious aspects as they were but not emphasizes data are presented fewer than three broad heads, such as procurement, sale of fish (wet) and dry fish and sale. Each head is further sub headed according to the info pertaining to type of marketing or domestic level besides the economic are dealt in detail to draw the domestic and entrepreneurial tenacities. Economic and fisher activities of women in coastal villages are analyzed using simple statistical technique. This study is based on the primary datasets and the output maps are prepared by the ArcGIS 10.2 software.

Introduction

Fisheries sector is an important source of food and nutritional security and livelihood for millions of people around the world. Economic growth is the result of overall sectors' development. The backbone of economic growth starts with the development of agriculture sector which provides foods for survival as well as base of development of subsidiary sectors of the economy. Fisheries sector is one of the important food production sectors in the State contributing to the livelihood as well as food security to a large

section of the economically under-privileged population. In fishery sector women play significant role in maintaining household and community needs.

Aims and Objectives

The present study aims at attempting an Economic and fishing activities of women in coastal villages of Nagapattinam district. The following are the major objective of the present investigation.

1. To examining conditions and role of marine fisher women of Nagapattinam district of Tamil Nadu.
2. To study socio- economic conditions of marine fisher women.
3. To study the women roles in economic and fishing activity

Review of Literature

The Nagapattinam district is a coastal district of Tamil Nadu state in southern India. The town of Nagapattinam is the district headquarters. It is a unique district with all its historical and cultural significance. The District of Nagapattinam lies on the shores of the Bay of Bengal between northern latitude of 10.10' and 11.20' and eastern longitude of 79.15 and 79.50'. The district capital, Nagapattinam lies on the eastern coast, 350 kilometres down south of the State capital Chennai and of Tiruchirappalli. Coastal length of the district is 188 Kms. The district boundaries are: East: Bay of Bengal. West: Tiruvarur district. North: River Kollidam and Cuddalore district. South: Palk Strait. Nagapattinam is one of the coastal districts in Tamil Nadu and is a part of the Cauvery river basin and delta. The Nagapattinam District even though agriculture and fishing are the major practices.

Figure 1 Location Map and Fisherman Villages

Methodology

The study is purely based on primary data mainly questionnaire. A sample of about 208 fisherwomen is selected and collected data on the socio-economic and cultural profile of fishing communities. Data are collected through predesigned schedule while collecting face-to-face interview. A few well informed women households are intensively questioned to draw in-depth information (case studies). The collected empirical data is analyzed and used as value addition to the observed socio-cultural and economic factors prevailing among the Nagapattinam fishing communities.

Results and Discussion

Self-help group (SHG) is a village-based financial intermediary committee usually composed of 10–20 local women or men. Members make small regular savings contributions over a few months until there is enough capital in the group to begin lending. Funds may then be lent back to the members or to others in the village for any purpose. In India, many SHGs are ‘linked’ to banks for the delivery of micro credit. In this aspect explains about fisher folk women’s awareness of self help group. Table no 1 show that 25 per cent females are aware about self-help group. Only 0 per cent females are unknown about self-help group. The other 75 per cent are males.

Table 1 Self Help Group Awareness

S No.	Awareness about Women Self Help Group	Respondents in Percentage
1	Yes	25
2	No	0
3	Other	75
	Total	100

Membership of Women Self Help Groups

Table no 2 explained that 15.86 per cent females got membership to the self help group. Then 7.22 per cent females are not joining the self help group. The other 76.92 per cent are males. Above 60 years age females are not considered for membership to the self-help group.

Table 2 Member of Self Help Group

S.No.	Member of Self Help Group	Respondents in Percentage
1	Yes	15.86
2	No	7.22
3	Other	76.92
	Total	100

Benefits from Self Help Group

The self-help group provides many benefits for the fishing communities. 14.91% of the fishing community get financial help from the Self Help Group and they get 85.09 other kinds of help from the financial help group. No one gets any help in the form of equipment or small savings.

Table 3 Benefits Obtaining from Self Help Group

S.No.	Benefits Obtaining from Self Help Group	Respondents in Percentage
1	Finacalass	14.91
2	Equpiement	0
3	Small Saving	0
4	Other Benefits	0
5	Other	85.09
	Total	100

Fish Trade/Per Day

Table no 4 indicate to measure street venture fish selling. The above 60 years old females are selling 5 to 7 kg fish in a day the accounted as 9.14 per cent. 3.85 per cent sell 7 to 9 kg of fish to sell

directly to hotels. 4.8 per cent sell 9 to 11 kg fish in a market or main junction or important places. 5.76 per cent sell the fish directly to the small agencies and big fish trade centres above 11 kg. The other 76.45 per cent are trade not measured (what they are captured to trade everything) the weight of fish to directly trade big commission agencies to near the shore.

Table 4 Selling of Fish in a Day

S.No.	Selling of Fish in a Day	Respondents in Percentage
1	5-7 KG	9.14
2	7-9 KG	3.85
3	9-11KG	4.8
4	less than 11KG	5.76
5	Other	76.45
	Total	100

Fish Selling Problem

Table no 5 explained that 26.45 per cent facing problem while fish selling. Then 73.55 per cent are not facing problem to fish selling. The street ventures and females are facing so many problems which are health problem transport problem head loading, fish unavailability, fish not selling at festival months these are the problems. Boat owners gathered the fish and reach the shore then sell it that is they don't have that much problem.

Table 5 Face Any Problem While Selling Fishing

S No	Face Any Problem While Selling Fishing	Respondents in Percentage
1	Yes	26.45
2	No	73.55
	Total	100

Special Training Programme

Table no 6 explains about fisherfolk attend the special training programmes. About 6.73 per cent attend self defence programme, and 6.73 per cent of fisherfolk attend awareness programmes. The other 61.54 per cent not attending any training and awareness programmes and training camp

Table 6 Benefit Available for Fisherman

S.No.	Benefit Available for Fisherman	Respondents in Percentage
1	Selt Defense	6.73
2	Awaerwess Prpgra	6.73
3	Machine Poertings Relates Training	0
4	No Training	61.54
5	Other	25
	Total	100
	Total Percentage	100

Conclusion

The present analysis aimed to understand about the socio cultural life of fisherfolk in Nagapattinam district. Women are involved in fish handling, processing and marketing. They also work as fish hawkers or run fish stalls in permanent market places or weekly bazaars. Drying and curing of fish is to a large extent done by women. Net making which is the main income-generating occupation is another important activity. In recent times, women engaged, in the marketing of fresh fish, face various problems, such as lack of cold storage facilities and appropriate fish preservation technologies, escalating cost of fish transportation and frequent strikes. They are also engaged in fish net making, raring, processing, washing, cleaning, salting, drying, and also packaging. They also work in some processing plants. The author gives suggestions to improve their condition. This is a more realistic approach and contribution to the development of women's participation in fisheries because the technical and economic problems faced by women already within the industry are many, and needs to be resolved. The field survey was carried out from 52 fisherfolk villages. Awareness about self-help group, membership of self-help group and related benefits. The present field observation help to explains about the women involved post harvesting fish related activities like curing, cleaning ,drying, selling of fish. The present field observation expose that they don't have proper fish selling shelter, net making place, equipment storage place and fish preservative centres. Mostly fisher men selling the fish in nearby the shore. All most the fisherfolk villages are connected main roads. A female worker makes brie fish shore and takes head loading to involve street vending activity.

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